

«CREATION OF THE STATUE OF AMIR TEMUR IN THE WORKS OF SCULPTOR ILHOM JABBOROV AND ITS PLACE IN THE ARTISTIC HERITAGE OF UZBEKISTAN»

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Annotation: The article deals with the creation of the statue of Amir Temur and the history of Amir Temur Avenue. Also, the perception of the image of Amur Temer as a national hero, the role of Temur's rule in the glorious future of our independence are also covered.

Keywords: alley, monument, sculpture, monument, symbols, bridle, culture, art.

Our independent Uzbekistan is an ancient country with a long history and rich culture, and is the only country in Central Asia. Like our country, it is rich in numerous monuments of ancient culture and enlightenment. The land of our republic is a unique and valuable resource that preserves the wonderful historical monuments of different periods from the emergence of mankind to the formation of major powers. Undoubtedly, the statue of Amir Temur erected on Amir Temur Avenue in Tashkent is one of the unique examples of sculpture. Amir Temur Avenue is a specially designated area of the city, a symbol of the initial coordinates. Culture, art, science are marked by a separate flourishing period.

The glorious history and great future of every state and society cannot be imagined without art. One of the brightest representatives of Uzbek sculpture, Ilkhom Jabborov Ilkhom Jabborov was able to create a school with his unique work and historical images. He was distinguished by his talent during his years of study at the Institute of Education and the Institute of Arts. Of course, the study of science and art depends on the loving skills of teachers. That is why the diversity and richness of the compositions in his works are obvious. In the works of Ilhom Jabborov began to appear very colorful sculptures. The sculptor was able to create the image of a number of historical scholars.

Among them, such works as "Ibn Sino", "Farabi", "Navoi and Jami", "Gafur Gulom" are especially noteworthy. The sculptor proved to be a master in modern sculpture, creating various compositions and colorful portraits. Ilhom Jabborov's work has been revived, revived, and made a serious effort to achieve creative maturity. He restored the image of the great commander Amir Temur in a monumental statue. Referring to the image of Timur, the sculptor states that he carefully interpreted the literature about the owner, miniatures, works of artists (p. 1.76-77).

- The dream of creating the image of Amir Temur first appeared to me many years ago. When I was in Samarkand, my heart trembled as if the spirit of our great ancestor was flying over me. When I visited Samarkand for the second time, I imagined the royal spirit guarding the city on a hill near Zarafshan. Centuries later, as they say, I arrived, I flew ... the idea of my statue was formed on the basis of this idea, the image born in the imagination. Timur brought culture to 27 countries, repulsed the tyrants, and wherever there was a revolt, he invaded and calmed them down. the statue depicts a horse holding the reins of a stamp as if it were ruling a large country with a symbolic meaning. As if peace and tranquility flourish in the country.

The sculptor admits that the idea was put forward. Indeed, Ilhom Jabborov is a mature artist who has boldly entered today's monumental sculpture and created his great works in this field. A. The choice of Temur as a symbol of the central part of Tashkent is not accidental. The image of the great commander and statesman, the founder of the Uzbek statehood, calls on the people of the capital to unite the independent state, to continue the noble deeds of the great ancestors. The statue depicts Amir Temur sitting on a horse.

The ruler is dressed in battle uniform, as if returning from a triumphant march, restraining his fiery horse with his left hand, his right hand rising above the people who greet him, and announcing that peace and tranquility will reign in the country. The majestic majesty of the ruler and the half-bent arm are a symbol of prosperity and progress. At the base of the statue, we see that the motto of the great Timur "Power is justice" is written in four languages. In the version presented by the sculptors, Sahibkiran was depicted holding a spear in his hand.

I objected to this, saying, "It is better for our grandfather Sahibkiran to hold the reins of a horse than a spear in his hand." - It has a symbolic meaning. Because there were many people in the kingdom who carried spears, but the reins were in the hands of Amir Temur. This means holding on to a solid state system.

At the same time, it would be expedient to raise the second hand of our great ancestor and wish it peace, happiness and prosperity to all people of the world.

In addition, in our nation, every action begins with the right hand, the right foot, reciting the Bismillah. In this statue, for some reason, the horse is stepping on his left foot.

Discussion participants agreed and the sculptors created a new option based on the ideas expressed. In 1996, on the occasion of the 660th anniversary of Amir Temur, practical work was carried out in Samarkand and Shahrisabz to erect a monument to our great ancestor. {2. Pages 14-15.}

In November 2009, in accordance with a government decision, Amir Temur Avenue was completely rebuilt: most of the old trees over the age of 100 were cut down. In the territory of the alley, a hashar was organized and changed beyond recognition, a beautiful, beautiful and cozy garden-alley was created. Various ornamental trees, flowers were planted and modern fountains were installed. As a result of the changes, the alley became brighter. Now the statue of Amir Temur in the great commander has created a more beautiful and finished composition, further reviving the modern look of our capital.

The tomb of Governor-General Konstantin Kaufman, who died in 1882 in Tashkent, was originally located in this alley. At the beginning of the last century, there was Constantine Avenue and the first sculptural composition in Tashkent was erected. From 1919 to 1926, the place was decorated with the monument "Sickle and Hammer", designed in the constructive style, which at that time served as a propaganda tool. After the war, the "master" of the alley became a statue of Stalin. In 1968, a monument to Karl Marx was erected. The monument "lived" until 1993, when the real people's hero - Amir Temur was elected.

Now the famous commander, who gave his name to the avenue and metro station in the center of the capital, is sitting on a war horse with dignity. The history of the place where the monument to the great commander Amir Temur is located was the richest period in the history of Tashkent. (3. 45-b) Alley History Kaufman Statue (1913); Kaufman Avenue (1913); Statue of Stalin (1953); Statue of Karl Marx (1977).

When thinking about the spiritual world of our great ancestors, it is natural to pay special attention to Sahibkiran Amir Temur. Because this classic figure, a symbol of unparalleled

determination, courage and wisdom, created a great empire. He left a practical and theoretical legacy in the field of statehood, paved the way for the development of science, culture, creativity, religion and spirituality. On August 31, 1994, on the eve of independence, well-known sculptors Ilhom Jabborov and Kamol Jabborov created the bronze statue of Amir Temur on horseback, which we see today, in such a magnificent view and presented it to Uzbekistan.

The statue of Amir Temur is the main monument in our city. Amir Temur was a powerful political figure and commander of the Middle Ages, who ruled for 200 years and formed a large and unique empire that stretched from the Caucasus to China and from Siberia to India. Timur's majestic standing and outstretched hand are a symbol of patronage, a promise of peace and tranquility to the people. We hope that our teachers Ilhom and Kamol Jabborov will be enriched with new examples of creativity, that they will live on the ancient Uzbek land for centuries.

References:

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2. I.A. Karimov "High spirituality is an invincible force" 14-15 p
3. "The Uzbek Monumental Sculpture of the Independence Period" p